

FAILURE CHARACTERISTICS IN A CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED METAL LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid composite laminates of aluminium alloy sheeting with unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy plies have been manufactured. The failure characteristics and mechanical property profile under static loading conditions were investigated. It is shown that these new Carbon Fibre Reinforced Metal Laminates (FRMLs) offer higher modulus, higher strength and lower density than their monolithic aluminium alloy counterparts. C-scan and chemical etching techniques were used to investigate the failure mechanisms in laminates with saw-cuts and circular cut-outs. Damage modes such as delamination, crack growth and fibre breakage are observed and progressive damage behaviour is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

It has been proven that laminated sheet material produced by adhesive bonding of a number of thin sheets has a higher fracture toughness when compared to the monolithic sheet material [1]. This is because the individual thin sheets allow plane stress dominant fracture to occur [2]. Also, in addition to high fracture toughness, high resistance to fatigue crack propagation is required in fatigue-critical structures such as the fuselage, lower wing skin and tail skins of aircraft. This latter requirement has led to the development of such novel metal/fibre composite laminates such as ARALL (Aramid Reinforced Aluminium Laminate), comprising layers of aluminium (0.3 mm thick) and aramid/epoxy (0.2 mm thick); and GLARE (glass fibres instead of aramid fibres). Recently, fatigue failures of old skins in aging aircraft has become a major safety issue. Because of the very good fatigue crack propagation resistance of these new metal/fibre composite laminates caused by the fibre reinforcements bridging the crack, they can be used in repair applications and as replacements for lightweight structural alloys.

The high fatigue resistance comes from the bridging fibres. If fatigue cracks occur in the aluminium sheets, the tough fibres can remain intact and bridge the crack. This results in a reduction of the crack opening displacement and the stress intensity factor at the crack tip [3], hence the reduction in the crack growth rate. FRMLs also offer additional benefits in that they can be cut, sawn, drilled and milled with conventional workshop practices. They also offer considerable weight savings of up to 30% compared with the use of monolithic

aluminium alloys [4].

Whilst a considerable amount of experimental data for both monotonic failure and fatigue crack growth exists in the literature for FRMLs, the available analysis is predominantly qualitative. Very little attention has been given to the failure characteristics of FRMLs such as delamination growth and crack growth in both the aluminium and composite layer. Such an understanding is necessary for accurate predictions of lifetimes and residual strengths of FRML structural components containing cracks/notches and circular cutouts.

The main objective of this study is to investigate the damage mechanisms and residual strength of carbon FRMLs with saw-cuts and circular holes of varying size. Results of mechanical properties are presented and compared with existing FRMLs and their monolithic counterparts. Delamination growth patterns (ie. size and shape) are determined together with a study of the crack growth mechanisms in the aluminium and composite layer under a quasi-static tensile loading condition.

MATERIAL PROCESSING

The material used in this work is a three-ply carbon fibre/metal laminate as shown in Fig. 1. It consists of two layers of 2024-T3 aluminium sheet in the clad condition and one layer of 59.4 wt% unidirectional carbon fibre epoxy composite, which consists of two plies of ICI Fiberite T300/7714A UD CF/Epoxy prepreg. The thickness of the aluminium sheets and the composite layer are 0.38 mm (0.015 inch) and 0.30 mm (0.012 inch) respectively. The composite layer is sandwiched between the two aluminium sheets with the fibres aligned in the aluminium rolling direction.

Figure 1. Schematic of a 3 ply carbon fibre/metal laminate.

The fabrication of the metal/fibre composites started with careful pretreatment of the aluminium sheet surfaces prior to bonding. The following procedures were used: hand abrasion, an acetone solvent wipe, washing in an alkaline solution at 60-70°C, a hot water rinse, etching in a sulfo-ferric solution at 60-65°C and air drying [5]. Bonding was achieved by curing in an autoclave under a pressure of 300 kPa at 120°C with the manufacturers approved curing cycle.

Dogbone tensile test specimens were cut from the panels in both the longitudinal and transverse directions. Tensile test coupons were 300 mm long and 12.5 mm wide with a 100 mm gauge length; no tabs were used. Residual strength specimens were 300 mm x 90 mm in size and were prepared individually from the 100 mm wide panels. A hole and/or saw-cut of 10, 20, 30 and 40 mm in size were introduced at the centre of the panels. Specimen preparation was achieved mainly with the use of an NC milling machine and saw-cuts were made with a 200 μ m jewellers saw blade. Specimen configurations are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Specimen configurations.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Tensile tests for measurement of Young's Modulus and tensile strength were carried out at room temperature on an Instron 5567 universal testing machine and the strain was monitored with a 25 mm gauge length extensometer. The crosshead speed was set at 5 mm/min and a minimum of five specimens for each case were tested in accordance with the tensile testing procedure for fibre metal laminates [6].

Residual strength tests were carried out on an Instron 1195 at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. All panels were non-destructively tested prior to testing to determine the extent of damage (if any) caused by machining. A minimum of three panels were initially tested to determine the residual strength results for each defect size. Panels were then incrementally loaded up step by step to the failure load and again C-scanned at each interval to determine the damage growth patterns. C-scan images were obtained via an ultrasonic immersion scanning system and confirmed using dye penetrant enhanced X-ray radiography. Crack growth in the aluminium sheets was monitored using a high resolution CCD (Charge Coupled Device) video camera with a 25 mm lens plus a 10 mm extension ring. The test equipment setup with the video camera is shown in Fig. 3. Selected panels with a saw-cut of 10 mm or 30 mm in length were subjected to detailed microscopic investigation of crack growth in the delamination area. For this purpose the aluminium layers on these panels were chemically etched away. Crack growth in the aluminium layer was measured with a 0.001 mm resolution travelling microscope prior to removal.

Figure 3. Test equipment setup for residual strength tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

A typical tensile stress-strain curve of carbon FRMLs along with the curves of each individual constituent are shown in Fig. 4. The tensile properties are summarised in Table 1 together with the commercially available FRMLs, a typical CFRP and the 2024-T3 alloy. In nearly all cases for the longitudinal specimens, tensile failure occurred in the gauge length radius region of the dogbone specimens. The transverse specimens failed within the gauge length. Similar failure modes have been observed with other FRMLs [7]. It can be seen that considerable improvements in strength, stiffness and density were obtained for the FRMLs over 2024-T3 aluminium alloy.

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves for Carbon FRMLs, carbon-epoxy prepreg and 2024-T3 sheet.

Table 1. Mechanical properties (longitudinal & transverse directions)

	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile yield strength at 0.2% offset (MPa)	% strain to failure	Density (g/cm ³)
2024-T3 L(0°)	63.7	437.8	322.1	-	2.79
	T(90°)	70	450.9	307.9	
CF/Epoxy ¹ L(0°)	114	1490	-	1.1	1.59
	T(90°)	-	-	-	
CFRML L(0°)	85.2	883	-	1.9	2.45
	T(90°)	53.9	304	238.6	
ARALL-2 ² L(0°)	64	717	359	2.5	2.33
	T(90°)	49	317	228	
GLARE-2 ³ L(0°)	65.6	1230	400	5.1	2.52
	T(90°)	50.2	320	230	

¹ From ICI Fiberite.

² ARALL-2: 2/1 lay-up of 2024-T3 + UD Aramid prepreg [8].

³ GLARE-2: 2/1 lay-up of 2024-T3 + UD R-glass prepreg [8].

RESIDUAL/NOTCHED STRENGTH

The residual/notched strength of Carbon FRMLs with the saw-cut and hole of various sizes is shown in Fig. 5. Although the strength of the panels is reduced more by the presence of the saw-cut, the saw-cut is not the more severe form of damage. Video monitoring reveals stable crack growth in the saw-cut specimens prior to unstable fracture, whilst the circular hole specimens exhibit no apparent crack growth prior to failure. Both specimen types exhibit sudden drops in the applied load above 90% of the ultimate load. This is associated with crack growth in the saw-cut specimens and with damage mechanisms in the circular hole specimens, such as delamination, fibre and matrix splitting, or fibre breakage in the composite layer. A greater reduction in the residual strength was observed for the specimens with a saw-cut.

C-scan images of the delamination patterns in the saw-cut and circular hole specimens are shown in Fig. 6 with the most obvious difference being the size and shape of the delamination patterns. A linear (triangular) delamination shape which grows in size as the crack grows, is associated with the saw-cut specimen, whilst the circular hole specimens exhibit a constant height delamination pattern at initiation. Also delamination did not initiate at the edges perpendicular to the applied load but at some angle (see Fig. 6c). With increased loading this delamination forms a semi-elliptical shape by the joining of the two delamination zones. Consequently this delamination zone was much larger than that associated with the saw-cut specimens. It is believed that this is due to stress concentrations in a larger field associated with the circular hole specimens. Once unstable fracture starts, the delamination zone height in the fibre direction depends on the crack path through the composite layer. Fibre pull-out as a result of failure away from the crack front caused a larger delamination height.

Figure 5. Residual strength ratio of a Carbon FRML in the presence of saw-cuts and circular holes.

Figure 6. C-scan images of the saw-cut and circular hole specimens.

The specimens with a 40 mm circular hole exhibited a different type of failure behaviour to the others. On loading the composite layer failed completely whilst the aluminium layer remained intact. Continued loading caused the aluminium ligaments to yield and eventually fail, which is attributed to the large delamination zone associated with this specimen. Delamination between the aluminium and composite layer results in a sudden increase in stresses sustained by the composite layer and because the strain to failure of the composite layer is much lower, early failure by stable crack propagation in the composite layer was observed.

To study the crack growth behaviour of the two specimens, the aluminium was chemically removed confirming the delamination patterns from the C-scan and allowing a visual examination of the crack in the composite layer. Fig. 7 shows a typical damage zone in the composite layer. Measurements of this zone compared with crack length measurements in the aluminium layer showed no signs of self similar cracking as observed by Macheret and Bucci [9]. This is possibly due to the large delamination zone evident in the present carbon fibre reinforced metal laminates. Again delamination would cause higher stresses in the composite layer. No reference was made to the delamination zone by Macheret and Bucci [9]. Table 2 lists the crack growth lengths observed in the aluminium and composite layer of the saw-cut specimens. Crack growth in the composite layer was also observed to coincide with the length of the delamination zone in the width direction (see Fig. 7).

Table 2. Crack length measurements in the saw-cut specimens.

Sawcut Length (mm)	Crack Length in the Aluminium Layer (mm)	Crack Length in the Composite Layer (mm)
10	3.495	10.150
20	1.666	5.075
30	2.697	6.661
40	1.177	3.489

Figure 7. Composite layer after removal of the aluminium layer.

CONCLUSIONS

The present carbon fibre reinforced metal laminates show improved tensile properties over their monolithic aluminium counterpart. A higher overall stiffness due to the stiffness of the carbon fibre layer is also shown over the commercially available grades of ARALL and GLARE.

The presence of saw-cuts and circular holes showed a drop in strength of greater than 40 %. The drop in strength is greater for the saw-cut specimens, however the circular hole may be considered the more severe form of damage as there is no apparent stable crack growth associated with its failure. Stable crack growth is observed in all layers of the saw-cut specimens. Delamination is suspected as the cause of unstable fracture without crack growth in the aluminium layer in the circular hole specimens. Large delamination areas may be a result of a poor interfacial bond strength between the aluminium and the composite layer.

The delamination pattern was found to be triangular for the saw-cut specimens up to the point of unstable fracture, whilst the circular hole specimens exhibit an elliptical shape with a constant height during damage progression in the composite layer. Delamination shape then depends on the crack path through the composite layer once unstable fracture begins. Chemical removal of the aluminium layer confirmed the delamination shapes observed with the C-scan and enhanced X-ray tests and microscopic inspection of the composite layer showed no signs of self similar cracking. In fact, cracking in the composite layer of the saw-cut specimens extended up to the length of the delamination zone in the width direction.

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